

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF CAPITAL INVESTMENTS ON THE INFLATION RATE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In this study, the influence of capital investments in our country on the level of inflation is widely covered on the basis of econometric analysis. In addition, factors affecting inflation were studied. During the research, the researches, results and conclusions of researchers and scientists who conducted scientific research in this field were studied on a large scale. The method of econometric modeling was used to determine the relationship between inflation and capital investments. During the research, the author used correlational regression analysis, tests such as Fisher's test and t-student, and the obtained results are shown in graphs and tables.*

Keywords: *inflation, foreign direct investment, econometric modeling, forecast value, correlation-regression analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

It is widely believed that inflation and investments hinder economic growth. As inflation reduces the purchasing power of money, interest rates also increase, resulting in lower real output. As the Fisher effect states, when inflation rises, nominal interest rates must also rise. The increase in interest rates has a negative effect on investments and, in turn, leads to a decrease in real GDP in the short term. General investments will decrease due to growth, and the change in interest rate will have a negative impact on both the demand for domestic investments and the volume of direct foreign investments.

The term "inflation" (Latin inflation - inflatable, expanding) was first used in North America during the civil war of 1861-1865 by the American economist A. Delmar, and it represented an excessive increase in paper money in circulation [1].

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on foreign direct investments said: "If we do not transfer the monitoring of project implementation to an automated system, we will not be able to identify problems in this regard in time. This system should provide practical assistance to foreign direct investment investors and facilitate their work"[2].

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities", investments are tangible and intangible assets and the rights to them, which are invested by the investor in the social sphere, entrepreneurship, scientific and other types of activities based on risks for the purpose of profit, including rights to intellectual property objects, as well as reinvestments, which may include:

funds, including cash (including foreign currency), targeted bank deposits, shares, bonds, promissory notes and other securities;

movable and immovable property (buildings, structures, equipment, machinery and other material values);

property rights related to intellectual property, including technical, technological, commercial documents, skills and production experience necessary for organizing this or that type of production, patented or unpatented (know-how) representation of one's knowledge, as well as other values not prohibited by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan[3].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, scientific studies show that there are different views among researchers and scientists about the relationship between inflation and direct foreign investment. For example, in the article of Abdul Majid Muhammad Mustafa, foreign direct investment is found as one of the important factors of the process of economic growth and development of Sri Lanka, and the high inflation rate directly affects the economy of Sri Lanka. It is widely reported that it affects the flow of foreign investments and slows down the process of economic growth and development. According to this study, he describes that "Low inflation rate is considered as a sign of internal economic stability in the country. A low inflation rate in the country leads to an increase in income from foreign direct investments. The dynamic contribution of foreign direct investment as a means of economic growth and development is very important for developing countries around the world"[4].

Korkmaz and Haghparast showed that there is no relationship between inflation and foreign direct investment in the period from January 2001 to March 2007. The results cast doubt on the claims of low inflation by international companies. Foreign companies are usually ready to invest in countries with low and stable microeconomic conditions[5]. Omankhanlen analyzed the impact of exchange rate and inflation on foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria for thirty years. Its results show that direct investment in some sectors is stimulated by economic growth with liberal trade policies. However, inflation does not have a statistically significant effect on direct investment. Exchange rate changes directly affect the flow of foreign investments[6].

Mangir, Ay and Sarach studied the determinants of direct investment in Poland and Uzbekistan using monthly data from 2000-2009. They used Granger causality test and vector autoregression model in the study. They came to the conclusion that the flow of direct investments has a positive relationship with the size of the market and the openness of the economy. Researchers did not find a connection between direct foreign investment and inflation in both countries[7]. However, Lee, Woodard, and Leatham found conflicting findings. They studied the causal structure between direct investment and economic growth and found that economic growth generates a direct flow of investment for developing countries. In contrast, direct investments stimulate economic growth in developed countries[8].

Yuce and Zelaya studied the foreign direct investment decisions of multinational companies in China and India between 2003 and 2008. Their results show that the large size of the market, high growth of the gross domestic product and low wages are the main factors of foreign direct investment decisions. Although the result of this study is indirectly related to our research, it makes sense because real wages decrease during inflation[9].

Alshamsi, Hussin and Azam studied the effects of inflation rates and GDP per capita on foreign direct investment in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) from 1980 to 2013. Their results show that inflation has no significant impact on the flow of foreign direct investment, while GDP per capita has a positive impact on the flow of foreign direct investment[10].

Tsaurai examines the impact of inflation on foreign direct investment, and using panel data analysis from 1995 to 2014, financial development is the direct driver of inflation in South Africa. He learned that it is a channel that can mitigate the impact on foreign investments. The results of the study show that under the fixed effect, inflation has a positive effect on foreign direct investment, but this is not statistically significant. However, if the random effect is taken into account, inflation has a negative effect on foreign direct investment, but this is not statistically

significant. On the other hand, under pooled OLS, inflation has a significant negative effect on FDI in South Africa[11].

Choban and Yussif examine the relationship between economic growth, foreign direct investment and inflation for Ghana from 1980 to 2017 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) model and the Toda and Yamamoto causality test. They show that inflation hinders FDI and economic growth, which means that inflation is negatively related to FDI and economic growth. They also found a bidirectional causal relationship between direct foreign investment and inflation. The reason for bidirectional causality is that inflation lowers real wages depending on the country where foreign investment has decreased in real terms. At the same time, foreign direct investment increases average income in the host country, which increases demand, which causes inflation[12].

METHODOLOGY

Objects in society and economy can be observed with the help of mathematical models. This concept is called modeling. The word model is derived from the Latin word modulus, which means measure, standard.

So, the validity of the model depends on the volume of the collected data, the level of accuracy, the experience and qualifications of the researcher and the modeling process, and the nature of the problem to be determined. It should not be forgotten that a very simplified model does not fully meet the set requirements, and on the contrary, a complex model creates difficulties in the process of solving it. Creating econometric models includes several steps.

The first step is specification. In this case, the economic problem is set - the group of main factors is selected, the economic problem is collected, the main factor and the group of influencing factors are determined: the factors participating in the model are determined using the method of correlation analysis.

The next step is identification, in which the parameters of the econometric model, which will be created with the help of the "Method of Least Squares", are determined. We use the system of normal equations to implement the "method of least squares".

The third stage is verification, and the importance of the created model is checked based on 4 directions.

1. The quality of the model is evaluated using the coefficient of determination:
2. The significance of the model is assessed using Fisher's criterion:
3. The reliability of the parameters of the model is evaluated based on the Student's criterion:
4. The significance of the "Method of Least Squares" is checked using the Durbin-Watson test.

The last stage. Using the developed and evaluated econometric model, the main economic indicators are calculated for the forecast period. The above-mentioned stages are inextricably linked and one complements the other and helps in the realization of a single goal.

RESULT

Macroeconomic stability of the country is directly explained by the growth rate of GDP. Investment activity is directly related to the macroeconomic stability of the country. If macroeconomic stability is ensured in the country, the volume of investments will increase. However, if macroeconomic stability is not ensured in the country, the risk of investors in investing

in this country will be high and confidence in the expected profit rate will be low. As a result, investors do not want to invest in this country. Another macroeconomic factor is inflation.

Figure 1. Dynamics of inflation and fixed capital investments in Uzbekistan (percentage)[13]

If we pay attention to the dynamics of inflation and fixed capital investments in Uzbekistan in 2010-2021, the following situation can be observed (Fig. 1). Direct inflation was the highest in 2018, as a result of which you can see an increase in the volume of investments in fixed capital in 2019. This, in turn, means that investments have an impact on inflation.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
inf	12	15.958	5.273126	8.931	26.981
capital	12	111.4917	12.17564	95.6	138.1

Figure 2. Descriptive statistical data of variables[14]

If we pay attention to the results of the analysis, inflation in the period of 2010-2021 was 15.95 percent on average, and investments in fixed capital were 111.49 percent on average. In the trend expressed in the graph, the highest inflation rate was 26.98 percent, while the lowest rate was 8.93 percent. Also, you can see that investments in fixed capital have the highest growth rate of 138.1 percent (Figure 2).

	inf	capital
inf	1.0000	
capital	0.5061	1.0000

Figure 3. Correlation analysis result[15]

In the course of the research, it was stated that there is a correct and moderately dense correlation between inflation and capital investments. This, in turn, means that there is no strong bond between them. We will conduct a regression analysis between them in the direct keying process.

Based on the results of the regression analysis, we created 4 different types of models. We performed the regression analysis process using the stata14 application package and obtained the results. At the same time, we presented the models in Table 1. Then we will check the regression

equations for quality tests at the next stage. For the purpose of comparing the results of the tests, we expressed them in tables in a comparative state (Table 2).

Table 1

Forms of regression equations[16]

Model name	Form
Linear model	$Inf = -8,48118 + 0,2192019 * Capital$
Hyperbolic model	$Inf = 42,21549 - 2898,252 * Capital$
Log-log model	$LnInf = -4,549847 + 1,544117 * LnCapital$
Liner-log model	$Inf = -103,679 + 25,40717 * LnCapital$

Table 2

Qualitative and significance tests of regression equations[17]

Model names	R ²	Root MSE	t-styudent		P> t		F (1,10)	Prob > F
Linear	0.256	4.769	-0.64	1.86	0.536	0.093	3.44	0.0932
Hyperbolic	0.249	4.79	2.92	-1.83	0.015	0.098	3.33	0.0980
Log-log	0.245	0.297	-1.13	1.80	0.286	0.102	3.25	0.1016
Liner-log	0.254	4.776	-1.60	1.85	0.141	0.095	3.41	0.0946

Analyzing the test results, the highest determination coefficient is in the linear model, the lowest RMSE value is in the Log-log model, the most positive t-student value of the parameters is in the linear model in terms of p-value, and according to the F-Fisher criterion, the linear model is the most optimal. We can also find the forecast value through the optimal model and do it through the trend model.

Table 3

Forecast value of inflation and fixed capital investments of the Republic of Uzbekistan[18]

Years	Inflation, GDP deflator: related series (annual, %)	Growth rate of investments in fixed capital, in %
2020	11,64	95,60
2021	13,56	102,90
2022	17,11	116,76
2023	17,29	117,57
2024	17,47	118,38
2025	17,65	119,19

According to the forecasting result it was empirically found that if fixed capital investments and inflation continue at this growth rate by 2025, inflation is 17.65 percent and fixed capital investments are 119.19 percent.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on available data, models and evidence from existing literature, this study shows the extent of the influence of investments in fixed capital in our country on the level of inflation. The main goal of this study is to study the impact of capital investments on the inflation rate. High

inflation causes a lot of uncertainty, has a negative impact on the development of the financial sector and the vulnerable poor strata of the population. In its place, the level of inflation also affects macroeconomic indicators. If macroeconomic stability is not ensured in the country, this creates risks in making investments in the country.

The study showed that in 2010-2021, in the dynamics of inflation and investments in fixed capital in Uzbekistan, the highest rate of inflation was observed in 2018, and as a result, the volume of investments in fixed capital increased in 2019. From this we can see that investments have an impact on inflation. In addition, a correlational analysis was conducted between inflation and capital investments. During the analysis, there is a connection between them in the correct and average density. It can be seen that there is a weak connection between them.

In the study, a regression analysis was also conducted between inflation and fixed capital investments. During the analysis, 4 different types of models were created. According to the results of the analysis, the most optimal model in all respects was considered a linear model. In conclusion, it should be said that as a result of forecasting, inflation will increase by 17.65 percent and capital investments by 119.19 percent until 2025.

Based on the results of our research, we would like to make several suggestions:

1. Ensuring the stability of the nominal exchange rate of the national currency in order to keep inflation within the same standard
2. Keeping inflation at a norm, it is necessary to reduce the circulation of cash funds, that is, the transition to electronic money to the development of e-commerce.
3. Introducing additional tax incentives to attract more investment.
4. Attracting investment, expanding the reach of small businesses and business sectors, that is, creating innovations.

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